

YASHIL

IQTISODIYOT
va
TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

RESPUBLIKA KONFERENSIYA (ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMAN) MAQOLA VA TEZISLAR TO'PLAMI:
"MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNI BARQAROR SAQLASHDA
"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT", "YASHIL MOLIYA",
"YASHIL BUXGALTERIYA" VA ILG'OR
MUHANDISLIK MAKTABLARINI ILMIY-AMALIY
INTEGRATSIYALASHTIRISH DOLZARBLIGI"

Konferensiya maqola va tezislari to'plami

2025-YIL
30-MAY

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 433 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 11-martda ruxsat etildi.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Omborxonada wms tizimidan foydalanishni afzalliklari.....	16
G'ofurov Shoxjaxon Abdumajit o'g'li, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdukarimovich	
Интеграция проектного офиса в корпоративную структуру строительной компании, работающей по ерс-контрактам.....	21
Махмудов Сардор Козим угли	
Investition muhit va unga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlili	24
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyati to'g'risidagi itimoiy-iqtisodiy qarashlar tahlili.....	27
Abduvohidov Behzod XXX	
Tijorat banklarida kredit portfelini boshqarishning asosiy yo'nalishlari.....	30
Jo'rayev Eldor Berdibekovich	
O'zbekistonda davlat budjetini kupaytirishda soliqlarni ahamiyati.....	34
Karimova Gulbahor Normurodovna	
Dunyo oziq-ovqat bozorining dinamik rivojlanishidagi o'zgarishlar, qiyinchiliklar va ularning yechimlari	36
Tolipova Baxtigul Farxodovna	
Исследование тепловых и диффузионных процессов при азотировании зубчатых колес в вакуумной среде	39
Жасурбек Юлдашбоевич Холмирзаев	
Axborot tizimlaridan foydalangan holda tashkilotni boshqarish bo'yicha qarorlar qabul qilishni takomillashtirish	49
Xujamova Shahrizoda Otabek Qizi	
Sanoat sektorida dekarbonizatsiya va qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalaridan foydalanish strategiyalari	52
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Sanoat rivojlanishini ekonometrik modellashtirish (Surxondaryo viloyati misolida)	56
Xalmuratov Zakirjan Mekkamovich	
"Yashil iqtisodiyot" – barqaror taraqqiyot omili.....	58
Lapasova Kamola Farhod qizi	
Umumta'lim maktablarida informatika fanini o'qitishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	60
Raxmonov Baxtiyor Azzamovich	
"Makroiqtisodiy masalalarni yechishda matematik modellarning ahamiyati"	63
Abdiraimov Abbas Xolmurod O'g'li	
Moda marketingida iste'molchilarning ichki ehtiyojlari va xulq-atvoriga asoslangan yondashuvlar	67
Tuxtaeva Oydiyoy Normamatovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida standartlashtirish siyosatida xalqaro tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlik tahlili	72
Raximov Ilyos Muydinovich	
Tijorat banklarida omonatlarni jalb qilishda mijoz sodiqligini oshirishga qaratilgan innovatsion yondashuvlar	75
Raximov Shoxrux Furqatovich	
Raqamli bank xizmatlarida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning istiqbollari va xavfsizlik masalalari.....	78
Erdonayev Aliqul Xalimovich	
Ta'minot zanjirini optimallashtirish yo'llari.....	82
Matkarimova Umida Alisher qizi, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdukarimovich	
The role of global value chains in international trade competition.....	85
Rakhmonova Dildora Ergash Qizi	
Электронная коммерция в узбекистане: государственные стратегии, технологический прогресс и барьеры развития.....	88
Махаммадалиева Муслимахон Шерали Кизи	

Modernization of the social protection system through digital technologies and innovative approaches.....	90
Abduzoirov Mukhiddin Umidjon ugli, Quدراتov Inomjon Nemat ugli	
Tabiiy va sun'iy tolalar asosida qayta ishlangan mahsulotlarning texnologik sifati va iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	93
Raximov Furqat Jalalovich	
Maishiy kimyo tovarlari B2B bozori uchun barqaror va yashil taqsimot modellarini ishlab chiqish.....	97
Ro'ziyeva Farzona Komiljon qizi	
Chakana savdo va xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish orqali hududiy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish	102
Po'latova Sug'diyona Iskandar qizi, Abdullayev Firdavs Sanjar o'g'li, Ravshanova Muxtarama	
Zamonaviy shahar massivlarida xizmat ko'rsatish va boshqarishda "Aqlli shahar" konsepsiyasi.....	105
Ismailov Najmiddin Ilxamovich	
Germaniyaning ta'minot zanjirlarini boshqarish tajribasidan foydalanishni afzalliklari.....	108
Nuriddinov G'ulomiddin Ziyovuddin o'g'li, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdukarimovich	
Ta'minot zanjirida CPFR texnologiyasi foydalanishni afzalliklari.....	111
Komilov Muhammad Yusuf Sardorbek o'g'li, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdukarimovich	
Ta'minot zanjirlarini qo'llashda jahon tajribasi.....	115
Karimov Amirxon Anvarovich, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdukarimovich	
Sug'urtada investisiya faoliyatini tashkil etishni huquqiy asoslari.....	118
Suyunov Isomiddin Tilovkobilovich	
Yurtimizda amaldagi budjetlararo munosabatlar tartibi, hisobi hamda uning afzalliklari.....	122
Po'latov Tirkash Sotiboldiyevich	
Aholini ijtimoiy himoya qilish institutlari shakllanishining xorij tajribalari	127
Bobonov N.H.	
Способ организации продуктивной работы преподавателя и его влияние на результативность	131
Гулнора Казимова	
Literature is a reflection of the soul and culture of humanity.....	136
Sayidova Sayyora Yorikulovna	
Turizm infratuzilmasida transport xizmatlarini integratsiyalash: muammo va yechimlar	140
Vakilov Ruslan Tillabayevich	
Ekoturizm va madaniy meros obyektlariga tashrifni tartibga soluvchi huquqiy normalar	142
Sayfiddinov Sharofiddinxo'ja Najmiddin o'g'li	
Strategies for achieving sustainable growth through green economy transition.....	145
Umida Kakhramonova Gayratovna	
Buxoro viloyatida qishloq xo'jaligida suv resurslaridan foydalanish samaradorligini oshirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar.....	149
Ro'ziyev Sobirjon Samatovich	
Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida mulkni qayta baholash va unga yetkazilgan moddiy zararni aniqlash.....	153
Xadjayev Kamoliddin Fazliddinovich	
Shahar aglomeratsiyasining sifatini ekologik va geologik mezonlar asosida kompleks baholash.....	155
Irgashev Shavkatbek Turdiyevich	
Sanoatda korxonalarining qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalari asosida barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishini ta'minlash	160
Qalandarova Gulshoda Nazirjon qizi	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida hududiy tengsizliklarni kamaytirish usullari.....	165
Ibragimov Baxrom Baxodirovich	
Tog' yon bag'rida joylashgan kon uymlarini ochiq usulda qazib olish xususiyatlari.....	174
I.T. Mislibayev, M.Sh. Ochilova	
Milliy iqtisodiyotda turizmning o'rni va rivojlanish imkoniyatlari.....	176
Xudoyberdiyeva Hilola Himmatovna	
China insurance market experience	178
Jumaboyev Akmal Sheraliyevich	

Tijorat banklarida moliyaviy resurslarning shakllanish manbalari.....	181
Tangirkulov Bekzod Boxadirovich	
Bank tizimida buxgalteriya hisobotlarida axborot texnologiyalarining roli va rivoji.....	185
Sodiqov Sanjar Saydullo o'g'li	
Samarali loyiha risklarini boshqarish: nazariya va amaliyot.....	189
Nosirova Gulira'no Abdulaziz qizi	
XXI-asrda Xitoyning iqtisodiy taraqqiyoti: sohaviy islohotlar, yutuqlar va muammolar tahlili.....	192
D.E.Qarshiyev	
Boshqaruv hisobining zamonaviy konsepsiyalarini joriy etish xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda natijadorlikka erishishning muhim omilidir	195
Xoshimov Baxrom Baxadirovich	
Eksportga chiqariladigan mahsulotlar uchun zamonaviy qadoqlashning ahamiyati va tendensiyalari	201
Xidirov Shohrux Bobur o'g'li	
Усовершенствование подходов к управлению проблемными кредитами в коммерческих банках узбекистана	205
Улмасой Хусан кизи Ахмедова	
Sug'urtada investitsiya faoliyatini obyekt va predmeti	208
D.E.Qarshiev	
O'zbekistonda raqamli texnologiyalarning tadbirkorlik sohasida istiqbollari.....	211
Sattarov Xayrulla Fayzullayevich	
Sug'urtada anderryating xizmatini xorij tajribasidan foydalanish.....	213
D.E. Qarshiev	
Важность проекта «умный город» в узбекистане	216
Акбаржон Иминов	
The role of digitalization of healthcare in the implementation of the safe city project	218
Akbarjon Iminov	
Moliyaviy faoliyat natijalari hisobini takomillashtirishda tahlilning o'rni.....	220
Po'latov Xudoyberdi Uktamovich, Abduxoliqov Isomiddin Ikrom o'g'li, Shakarov Shahzod Sobir o'g'li	
Temir yo'l va intermodal transport tizimining rivojlanishi: investitsiyalar, xarajatlar va samaradorlik tahlili	226
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
O'zbekistonda qishloq xo'jaligini barqaror rivojlantirish uchun xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish ahamiyati.....	230
S.J. Yangiboev	
Korporativ boshqaruv va moliyaviy barqarorlik o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik: davlat ishtirokidagi korxonalar misolida.....	234
Musurmonov Mehroj Murtaza o'g'li	
“Sanoat korxonalarida zamonaviy loyiha menejerining asosiy kompetensiyalar modelini ishlab chiqish”	238
Axmedov Daniyar Sabirovich, Valiyev Shamsiddin Eshpulatovich	
Turizmdagi shartnoma munosabatlari: turoperatorlar, turagentlar, turistik xizmatlar iste'molchilari.....	241
Ergasheva Iroda Ibrohim qizi	
“Разработка модели ключевых компетенций современного менеджера проекта в промышленных предприятиях”	243
Ахмедов Данияр Сабирович, Научный руководитель	
Xorijiy tajriba asosida o'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim akademik boshqaruvini takomillashtirish	249
Muxamedova Moxigul Xusanovna	
The role of international institutions in accelerating green finance	253
Qudratov Inomjon Nemat o'g'li	
Barqaror iqtisodiy o'sish sharoitida yashil innovatsiyalar va raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirish	257
Xudayberdieva Dilnoza Egamberdiyevna	
Indicators and criteria of women's sustainable employment in the context of economic growth.....	262
Kholiyorova Shokhista Kahramon kizi	
Qishloq xo'jaligi sohasida “Salam” maxsus savdo shartnomalaridan foydalanish istiqbollari.....	267
Xoliyrov Xomid	

Davlat xaridlarida kichik biznesning ortib borishi va uning umumiy tizimdagi o'рни	269
Majidov Nizom Baxramovich	
Davlat qarzlari qaytarish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish va tashqi xatarlardan himoyalash yo'nalishlari	273
Sayfutdinov Xasanboy Dilshodovich	
Xalqaro moliya institutlaridan investitsiyalarni jalb qilishning ahamiti	277
Tolibov Shoxrux Muminovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasining soliq salohiyati: 2024-yilda viloyatlar va Qoraqalpog'iston	280
Poyonov Otabek Abdiqaxxor o'g'li, Almardonov Muxamadi Ibragimovich, Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida investitsiya muhitini boshqarishning institutsional mexanizmlari	283
Otaxanov Rasulbek Marks o'g'li	
Автоматизированное управление корпоративными расходами: стратегический подход и экономическая эффективность	286
Кахоров Абдумалик Рахматулло угли	
Повышающаяся значимость коренного изменения деятельности традиционных СМИ в реалиях освещения процесса построения нового Узбекистана	289
Салим Дониёров	
Raqamli transformatsiyaning mohiyati va bank sohasidagi ahamiyati	294
Kamolov Sardorbek Davlatjon o'g'li	
Деятельность международных финансово-кредитных организаций и перспективы развития сотрудничества с Республикой Узбекистан	299
Холикова Зарнигор Камолиддин кизи	
Budjet tashkilotlarining xarajatlar smetalarida davlat xarajatlarini moliyalashtirish tartibi va amal qilish holati	302
Abdurasulov Sardor To'liqin o'g'li	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan kompayens-nazorat tizimini rivojlantirish istiqbollari	307
Rustamov Sunnatillo Rustamovich	
Bank tizimi modernizatsiyasida innovatsion boshqaruv modellarining ahamiyati	310
Hamroyev Xurshid Jalilovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya	314
Turapov Bahromjon Alisher o'g'li	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida yashirin iqtisodiyotni qisqartirishga yo'naltirilgan davlatning siyosati, me'yoriy-huquqiy bazasi va iqtisodiy islohotlari	317
Xasanov Jaxongir Jamshidovich	
"Qurilish materiallari sanoatida innovatsion faollikni rag'batlantirish mexanizmi"	321
G'ulomov Ilhom Akramovich	
Legal foundations and challenges in the implementation of guarantees for foreign investors' rights	324
Alisherova E'zoza, N. Kh. Rakhmonqulova	
Innovatsion faollikni oshirish orqali qurilish materiallari sanoatida raqobatbardoshlikni ta'minlash	326
G'ulomov Ilhom Akramovich	
Soliq siyosatining inklyuziv rivojlanishni ta'minlashining huquqiy-me'yoriy asoslari	329
Hakimov Feruz Xurshid o'g'li	
Транснациональные корпорации и международное право: к формированию глобальных экономических норм через расширение правосубъектности	334
Хидоятов Бурхон Ғайрат ўғли, С.М. Адилходжаева	
O'zbekistonda yashirin iqtisodiyotning hozirgi holati va uni shakllantiruvchi omillar	338
Malikov Abdulaziz Toxirjon o'g'li, S.A. Zakirova	
Abxidjit Banerdji va Ester Dyuflo ilmiy qarashlarida kambag'allikni qisqartirish istiqbollari	343
M.E.Rajabboyev	
Transport va logistika infratuzilmasini modernizatsiya qilish orqali eksport samaradorligini oshirish	346
Kurbonova Ma'mura Abdukarim qizi	
Fond bozori vositasida iqtisodiyotni moliyalashtirishning usullari	350
G'aniyev Axrorjon Norboy o'g'li	
Davlat moliyaviy nazorati tizimida ichki audit xizmati faoliyatining amaliy jihatlari	354
Kuliyev Komil Shuxratovich	
Digitalization in economy	358
Razzaqov Jasur Xamraboevich, Yaqubov Matrasul Mavlonberdiyevich, Sabirova Nodira Komil qizi	

Sirkulyar iqtisodiyot tamoyillariga asoslangan yashil investitsiya strategiyalari.....	361
Hakimov Anvarjon Abdulloyevich	
Sun'iy intellekt yordamida quritilgan organik mevalar eksportida marketing strategiyalarini optimallashtirish.....	363
Xidirov Shohrux Bobir o'g'li	
Ziyorat turizmini rivojlantirishda zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish.....	372
Zaripov Toxirjon Yusufboy o'g'li	
Hududlarda ayollar bandligini ta'minlash orqali investitsion muhitni yaxshilash yo'llari	376
Imomova Kamola Novfal qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH TIZIMIDA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI	381
Solikhova Dildora Alisher qizi	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYASI: IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK VA INNOVATSIYA BOSHQARUVI	384
Mansurova Sayyora Baxtiyor qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONNING IT-XIZMATLAR EKSPORTI GEOGRAFIYASI 2024-YIL NATIJALARI	387
Jumaboyev Akmaljon Sheraliyevich	
O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	391
Abdurazaqov Jasur Abdunasimovich	
TURIZM SOHASIDA MIJOZLAR SODIQLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MARKETING KOMMUNIKATSIYALARINING AHAMIYATI	397
Shaymanov To'liqin Mahmayusopovich	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASHDA SOLIQ SIYOSATINING SAMARADORLIGI.....	400
Sheraliyev Nurbek Jumanazarovich	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIDA TURIZMNING O'RNI: GLOBAL VA MAHALLIY TAHLIL.....	402
Xamdullayeva Gulhayo Ergash qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON EKSPORT TARKIBINI YUQORI QO'SHIMCHA QIYMATLI MAHSULOTLARGA O'TKAZISH STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	404
Raximov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
EKSPORT FAOLIYATIDA ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONALARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	408
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
SIYOSIY ISLOHOTLAR VA GLOBALLASHUVNI O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIGA TA'SIRI.....	411
Xalilova Sevaraxon Alijon qizi	
MOLIYAVIY XIZMATLAR SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHDA XALQARO TAJRIBA	414
Muyassarzoda Fayziyeva	
MILLIY MOLIYA BOZORI JORIY HOLATI TADQIQI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	417
Samadov Temur Oybek o'g'li	
ELEKTRON TO'LOV XAVFSIZLIGI: ZAMONAVIY TAHDIDLAR VA HIMOYA MEXANIZMLARI	421
Toxirov Shodibek Jo'ra o'g'li	
MAMLAKAT MAKROIQTISODIY BARQARORLIGINI TAMINLASHDA TASHQI SAVDO SIYOSATINING O'RNI.....	424
Alimova Dilfuzaxon Rustam qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA G'AZNACHILIK TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH ORQALI DAVLAT MOLIYASI BOSHQARUVINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	427
Tangrieva Farida Abdukarimovna	
DEVELOPING TOURISM THROUGH VIRTUAL AND AUGMENTED REALITY TECHNOLOGIES.....	431
Olimov Davron Olimovich	

DEVELOPING TOURISM THROUGH VIRTUAL AND AUGMENTED REALITY TECHNOLOGIES

Olimov Davron Olimovich

Senior Lecturer, Department of Tourism,
Kimyo International University in Tashkent
davronolimov@inbox.ru
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-0524-2375>

Abstract: The thesis analyzes the use of Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) technologies in tourism development, focusing on Uzbekistan's potential. It discusses how immersive technologies enhance marketing, visitor engagement, and sustainability. Despite infrastructural and professional challenges, Uzbekistan's cultural heritage and digital strategy create favorable conditions for VR/AR implementation.

Key words: virtual reality, augmented reality, tourism, Uzbekistan, digital transformation, sustainability.

Annotatsiya: Tezisdagi virtual (VR) va kengaytirilgan (AR) realistik texnologiyalarining turizmni rivojlantirishdagi roli, ayniqsa O'zbekiston imkoniyatlari misolida yoritilgan. Immersiv texnologiyalar marketing samaradorligini, sayyohlar tajribasini va barqaror rivojlanishni oshirishi ta'kidlanadi. Mavjud muammolarga qaramay, mamlakatda VR/AR joriy etish uchun qulay sharoitlar mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: virtual realistik, kengaytirilgan realistik, turizm, O'zbekiston, raqamli transformatsiya, barqarorlik.

Аннотация: В тезисе рассматривается использование технологий виртуальной (VR) и дополненной (AR) реальности в развитии туризма, с акцентом на потенциал Узбекистана. Показано, что иммерсивные технологии повышают эффективность продвижения, вовлеченность туристов и устойчивое развитие. Культурное наследие и цифровая стратегия создают благоприятные условия для внедрения VR/AR.

Ключевые слова: виртуальная реальность, дополненная реальность, туризм, Узбекистан, цифровая трансформация, устойчивость.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the fastest-growing and most dynamic sectors of the global economy, contributing significantly to GDP, employment, and cultural exchange. In recent years, the tourism industry has undergone a profound digital transformation driven by new technologies, particularly Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR). These technologies have redefined how destinations are marketed, how experiences are delivered, and how tourists interact with cultural and natural heritage.

Virtual Reality provides complete immersion in a simulated environment, allowing users to explore attractions or events as if they were physically present. Augmented Reality, on the other hand, enhances real-world experiences by overlaying digital information—such as images, sounds, or text—onto physical surroundings through smartphones or smart glasses. Both technologies are revolutionizing the way tourism organizations engage with potential visitors and how tourists experience destinations.

According to Guttentag (2010), Virtual Reality in tourism provides unique opportunities for pre-experience marketing by offering potential travelers a realistic sense of place. Later studies by tom Dieck and Jung (2018) highlighted the value of AR for enhancing on-site experiences, such as museum visits or city tours. Similarly, Han et al. (2020) noted that immersive technologies can evoke emotional engagement, influencing tourists' satisfaction and decision-making.

In the context of destination marketing, VR and AR technologies allow tourism boards to create interactive campaigns that go beyond traditional advertising. For example, destinations such as Singapore, South Korea, and Dubai use VR experiences to showcase attractions online, allowing users to "visit" virtually before making travel decisions. These practices not only strengthen the competitive position of destinations but also reduce marketing costs and environmental footprints.

Research also emphasizes the role of VR and AR in sustainable tourism. By enabling virtual exploration of fragile ecosystems, heritage sites, or protected areas, these technologies reduce physical pressure on sensitive environments. According to Yung and Khoo-Lattimore (2019), virtual tourism can serve as an alternative form of travel during crises, such as pandemics or natural disasters, ensuring the continuity of cultural exchange and education.

The adoption of VR and AR technologies in Uzbekistan's tourism sector remains in its early stages, but the potential is enormous. The country's rich cultural heritage, historical monuments, and diverse natural landscapes provide a strong foundation for immersive storytelling. Through VR, tourists can virtually walk through Registan Square in Samarkand or explore the ancient city of Khiva. With AR, museums could bring artifacts to life through interactive displays, offering deeper understanding and engagement for visitors.

Furthermore, VR and AR can play a crucial role in promoting inclusive tourism—offering opportunities for elderly and disabled individuals to experience destinations that may otherwise be inaccessible. Such applications align with global trends in digital transformation and sustainability, enhancing both economic and social inclusiveness.

Despite these opportunities, several challenges remain, particularly those related to infrastructure, costs, and human resource capacity. Many tourism organizations in Uzbekistan lack the technical expertise required to design and implement immersive technologies. Therefore, collaboration among universities, technology companies, and the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection, and Climate Change is essential to create an enabling ecosystem for innovation.

Moreover, integrating VR and AR technologies into national tourism promotion campaigns can attract younger audiences and diversify the tourism product portfolio. For example, developing virtual tours of UNESCO World Heritage sites in Uzbekistan could enhance global visibility and attract international tourists interested in cultural and educational experiences.

CONCLUSION

Virtual and Augmented Reality are reshaping the global tourism landscape by offering immersive, personalized, and sustainable travel experiences. For Uzbekistan, the integration of these technologies represents a strategic opportunity to strengthen its international image, enhance visitor satisfaction, and support sustainable development goals.

To achieve these objectives, policymakers and industry leaders should prioritize:

Investment in digital infrastructure and professional training;

Development of VR/AR-based content for cultural heritage and ecotourism;

Support for startups and innovation in tourism technology;

Integration of immersive technologies into tourism education and marketing strategies.

By leveraging VR and AR, Uzbekistan can position itself as a forward-looking tourism destination—one that seamlessly blends tradition with innovation in the era of digital transformation.

REFERENCES

1. Buhalis, D., & Sinarta, Y. (2019). Real-time co-creation and nowness service: Lessons from tourism and hospitality. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 36(5), 563–582. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10548408.2019.1578798>
2. Cheong, R. (1995). The virtual threat to travel and tourism. *Tourism Management*, 16(6), 417–422. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0261-5177\(95\)00049-V](https://doi.org/10.1016/0261-5177(95)00049-V)
3. Guttentag, D. A. (2010). Virtual reality: Applications and implications for tourism. *Tourism Management*, 31(5), 637–651. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2009.07.003>
4. Han, D. I. D., Jung, T., & Gibson, A. (2020). Dublin AR: Implementing augmented reality in tourism. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 33, 100–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2019.100618>
5. Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change of Uzbekistan. (2023). *Digital transformation in tourism strategy 2030*. Tashkent: Government Press.
6. Tom Dieck, M. C., & Jung, T. H. (2018). A theoretical model of mobile augmented reality acceptance in urban heritage tourism. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 21(2), 154–174. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2015.1070801>
7. Tussyadiah, I. (2020). A review of virtual reality as a medium for tourism experiences. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 113, 106440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106440>
8. Yung, R., & Khoo-Lattimore, C. (2019). New realities: A systematic literature review on virtual reality and augmented reality in tourism research. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 32, 100–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2019.100712>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025-yil, may.

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.
Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
